

Windows on Data: Federating Research Data with FAIR Digital Objects and Linked Open Data

A Cross-Consortia Use Case from Engineering Science and Humanities

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Abstract

Against the background of the vision of ‘One NFDI’, consortia are increasingly faced with the question of overarching metadata models and common metadata standards. In material culture, built environment or cultural heritage, interdisciplinary collaboration between engineering and natural sciences, humanities and social sciences is essential for scientific success but involves multiple consortia. Making the best possible use of cross-NFDI cooperations, the consortia have set up a standing working group with the aim of finding concrete solutions in transdisciplinary research data management.

An exemplary use case is centered on medieval stained-glass windows from the Corpus Vitrearum Medii Aevi (CVMA) project¹ [1], [2], which allows the consortia DAPHNE4NFDI, MaRDI, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects, NFDI4ING, and NFDIxCS to examine data types, processes and implementations for FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) [3], [4], Linked Open Data (LOD) [5]–[11] or Knowledge Graphs [12], [13]. The research project CVMA catalogs Medieval stained glass in Germany based on high resolution photographic images enriched with information regarding history and conservation [14], bibliography, related actors, iconography and location. The project integrates methodologies and existing standards from art history, conservation, digital imaging, and information science. This use-case can be extended to include measurements and process data of various kinds, e.g., photogrammetry [F1;F4;F5], x-ray scans [N1;N2;F2], microscope analysis [F3], and goniophotometric scatter analysis [N3]. These data generation processes fall within the domains of material, engineering, and natural sciences, so

¹cf. <https://corpusvitrearum.de>.

the tools and standards of the related consortia apply. Ideally, this data and other artefacts such as software, measurement, simulation setups or calibration data is stored in the form of a FDO containing technical metadata regarding its content and type and a Persistent Identifier (PID) to make it findable. A federated infrastructure for generating and storing FDO is currently under development.

At the same time, research data is provided within KGs, e.g., Culture Knowledge Graph² or the N4O KG³. These data may include rich semantic annotations, topographical and architectural contexts, 3D documentation and conservation history. Reference data models such as CIDOC CRM⁴ (including LIDO⁵), schema.org⁶, BFO⁷, DCAT⁸ and NFDIcore⁹ can be applied for interoperability. Workflows¹⁰ based on RDM incl. proposed tools provided by DAPHNE4NFDI¹¹ can be easily integrated and partially or completely reused.

In this context, MaRDI [15] explores how mathematical and computational methods can support the transformation of FDOs into semantically integrated Knowledge Graphs. Techniques such as metadata enrichment, pattern detection, and clustering can be applied to structure, harmonise, and relate FDO contents across domains. This enables the alignment of heterogeneous metadata models and facilitates their translation into interoperable representations.

A key question for future work is how to interconnect paradigms like RDF, LPG and FDOs into existing knowledge graph infrastructures (Fig. 1). Here, Basic Services such as TS4NFDI or KGI4NFDI offer solutions for aligning and federating metadata [13]. Terminology services and the emerging NFDIcore Ontology will be central to supporting cross-consortia interoperability. These aspects will be further explored and discussed in the context of this paper and the joint efforts across NFDI consortia.

Keywords: Engineering, Humanities, Linked Open Data, FAIR Digital Objects, Knowledge Graph, community-standards, NFDIcore Ontology, CIDOC-CRM

²cf. <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E2391> and <https://nfdi4culture.de/go/kg-kitchen-dashboard>.

³cf. <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/> and <https://nfdi4objects.github.io/n4o-graph/>.

⁴cf. <https://cidoc-crm.org/>.

⁵cf. <https://www.lido-schema.org>.

⁶cf. <https://schema.org/>.

⁷cf. <https://basic-formal-ontology.org/>.

⁸cf. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>.

⁹cf. <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>.

¹⁰cf. <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/77.php>.

¹¹cf. <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/index.php>.

Figure 1. FDO / LOD federated Knowledge Graph in the context of scientific production in engineering and the humanities.
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Resources

Figures

- Figure 1. [GitHub:Fig-01](#). “FDO / LOD federated Knowledge Graph in the context of scientific production in engineering and the humanities. CC BY 4.0, Florian Thiery and Andreas Noback.”

Related Tools & Services

- Semantic Kompakt. [GitLab:wikibase4research](#). “Semantic Kompakt is a free and open source toolchain for the viewing and annotation of 3D models, and other visual media within a linked open data (LOD) environment, via <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E3752>.”
- Wikibase4Research. [GitHub:jupyter-nb-lod](#). “Wikibase4Research is a free and open source suite of tools for the storage and management of Linked Open Data (LOD), via <https://nfdi4culture.de/id/E3759>.”.

Related Ontologies

- NFDI4Culture Ontology (CTO). <https://nfdi.fiz-karlsruhe.de/4culture/ontology/>. “CTO is a domain-specific ontology module developed within the Task Area 5 of the NFDI4Culture initiative. The ontology builds upon the NFDIcore mid-level ontology and is aligned with the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) 2020 to ensure semantic interoperability and ontological rigor. CTO represents the research data of the NFDI4Culture community within a research data index, i.e. a single point of access to decentralized cultural heritage research resources.”.
- NFDIcore Ontology. <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>. “The National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative has led to the formation of various consortia, each focused on developing a research data infrastructure tailored to its specific domain. To ensure interoperability across these consortia, the NFDIcore ontology has been developed as a mid-level ontology for representing metadata related to NFDI resources, including individuals, organizations, projects, data portals, and more.”.
- Linked Archaeological Data Ontology (LADO). <https://wissit.pages.gitlab.rlp.net/lado/index-en.html>. “A CIDOC-CRM referenced ontology within the data hub archaeology.link at LEIZA”.
- Archaeo-Natural Ontology (ArNO). <https://archaeonatural-cloud.github.io/archaeonatural-ontology/>. “Ontology containing classes to describe Jannofiles of the data of NFDI4Objects Task Area 3: currently Poseidon, soon ArboDat & Ossobook.”.

Related Linked Open Data

- archaeology.link. <https://archaeology.link>. “ARCHAEOLOGY.LINK presents research data, ontologies, related research tools and web services for e.g., Linked Open Data technologies within the scope of the archaeological basic research carried out by the LEIZA and its cooperation partners in joint projects. This platform complements the LEIZA Archaeological Data Processing Web Service (ADP).”.

- Linked Open Ogham. <https://linkedopenogham.github.io/ogham-lod/>. “This repository contains Ogham Data of several data sources such as Celtic Inscribed Stones Project (CISP), Ogham in 3D Project, Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum (1945). The data belongs to the Irish Stones in the Wikimedia Universe project. This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland and the Open Science Fellows Program.”.
- Linked Open Ogham. <https://linkedopenogham.github.io/ogham-lod/>. “This repository contains Ogham Data of several data sources such as Celtic Inscribed Stones Project (CISP), Ogham in 3D Project, Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum (1945). The data belongs to the Irish Stones in the Wikimedia Universe project. This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland and the Open Science Fellows Program.”.

Related Process Data

- **[N1]** Processed model of a Computed Tomography scan of Roman window glass from Ephesos. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13759479>. “The model is based on a tomography scan on an antique window glass fragment from Ephesos (today Efes, Turkey). The sample was contributed by the Austrian Archaeological Institute, Vienna, and has the inventory ID EVH12/1017/1322.”.
- **[N2]** Computed tomography scan of Roman window glass from Ephesos. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5651890>. “Computed density scan of a window glass sample performed at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (Luci, <https://www.hslu.ch/luci>). The glass fragment from Ephesos was provided by the Austrian Archaeological Institute (inventory ID EVH12/1017/1322), Vienna, Austria.”.
- **[N3]** Light Scattering by Roman window glass. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3265014>. “This archive contains data-sets representing the light scattering properties of four samples of Roman window glass, as described in detail in Grobe, Noback, and Lang. Data-Driven Modelling of Daylight Scattering by Roman Window Glass.”.
- **[F1]** 3D meshes of wood samples. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10477778>. “The repository contains 3D meshes of 83 wood samples from the LEIZA reference collection, which were created within the framework of the project “Mass Finds in Archaeological Collections”. About 10 years later, the surface of the wood samples selected for the CuTAWAY project was again digitized using a 3D structured light projector (GOM ATOS III Triple Scan Rev.02) with a resolution of 0.10 mm.”.
- **[F2]** Cross-sectional images from x-ray computed tomography (XCT) of conserved archaeological samples. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12690014>. “The repository contains cross-sections of 83 wood samples derived from X-ray computed tomography (CT) data.”.
- **[F3]** Reflected light microscope images of conserved waterlogged archaeological wood. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10726106>. “The repository contains images of conserved archaeological wooden samples captured in a reflected light microscope as part of the cutaway project.”.
- **[F4]** Adlerstein (NLRMR-36638) 3D Mesh. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301659>. “3D Mesh of a “Adlerstein” near Aachen (Germany) and Vaals (Netherlands) created with the KIRI engine App.”.

- [F5] Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15301838>. “3D Mesh of Ogham Stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4 at UCC cork, created with the KIRI engine App.”.

Author contributions

The list of authors is sorted in alphabetical order and has contributed according to CreDIT: Conceptualization: all authors in collaboration; Methodology: Andreas Noback and Florian Thiery on the federated NFDI Knowledge Graph Ecosystem; Writing – original draft: all authors in collaboration.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

This work is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under the National Research Data Infrastructure. DFG project numbers: NFDI-MatWerk (460247524), NFDI4ING (442146713), NFDI4Culture (441958017), DAPHNE4NFDI (460248799), NFDIxCS (501930651).

K. Fischer, A. Gerber and F. Thiery are supported by the “Research Data Infrastructure for the Material Remains of Human History (NFDI4Objects)”, DFG project number: 501836407.

T. Koprucki and M. Reidelbach are supported by “MaRDI – Mathematische Forschungsdateninitiative”, DFG project number: 460135501.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the DFG and the GWK for funding the NFDI consortia and also our communities for being active in this dynamic, interdisciplinary, bottom-up RDM initiative.

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